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Model based engineering for improved SOFC system development

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Abstract

SOFC system development is an interdisciplinary task with some challenging goals to combine: fast heat-up, high efficiency, controllability, part-load operation, high power density, and on top - fuel flexibility. To reach all mentioned goals extraordinary expertise in a broad field of disciplines is required on system, sub-system, and component level. Hence, a model based engineering approach provides the possibility not only to achieve the goals, but also to achieve them in a more cost and time efficient manner by.

AVL has more than 50 years of experience in drive train and drive train component development. Using a classical automotive V-Model approach, the application requirements will be used as an input, to define the requirements of the SOFC system. All further development tasks are then coordinated by the model based engineering approach. For system simulation, AVL has a comprehensive library of physical models for all components necessary and typically used within SOFC/SOEC systems. This library can be easily updated by empirical models using neuronal networks (NN) for fast and efficient implementation. Using the AVL integrated open development platform (IODP) allows to better connect all mentioned and additional tools, such as active design of experiments (active DoE) and pinch analysis independently from both virtual and real world. Further, any experimental validations are fed back to the model based engineering approach via IODP. Having this feedback, the design process is driven by the latest performance data available. This approach provides the possibility of highly efficient SOFC system development from the first idea to serial production; limited only by the boundaries of the real world.

Introduction

SOFC system development is an interdisciplinary task. When starting from a blank paper the following stages are usually be part of the development approach: (i) development of system architecture, (ii) process simulation, (iii) design integration, (iv) design implementation, (v) control strategy, and (vi) system validation. The described order does not necessarily have to follow the before mention one but is influenced by logical sequence and development philosophy. However, these different stages are usually processed by different people with different background and technical knowledge. Hence, a clear process and work flow, as well as good communication within the development team is crucial in order to keep the cost to a minimum and to avoid errors appear late in the development process. Because such late detected errors are typically more costly than errors corrected early in the process [1].

The broad scope of application of the SOFC/SOEC technology (e.g. combined heat and power, range extender, electrolyzer) [2] is further challenging because different applications require different system architectures, design integrations, design implementations, etc. with varying focuses on e.g. efficiency, durability, controllability, etc. This complex structure of influence parameters on the development approach require a more flexible work flow without losing its clear structure.

Modeling of complex systems such as SOFC/SOEC systems is crucial to better understand influence parameters and detect errors in an early stage of the development process. The modeling is thereby not limited to any level of detail but usually starts at high-level (very little details) and ends at low-level including already specific component characteristics such as mass, geometry, and e.g. temperature limitations. The change in level of detail can thereby take place at different stages within the development process and needs to be coordinated in an effective manner.

Within this paper the V-model from the automotive industry is used to describe and define the work flow for improved SOFC system development by using high- and low-level simulation at various stages.

1. Scientific Approach

Increasing complexity of SOFC systems require new development approaches. This becomes even clearer when considering the increasing demand in efficiency, controllability, and life time. Hence, traditional mechanical-oriented development approaches are overtaken. Such change in development strategies has already taken place in the automotive industries and new comprehensive approaches, such as the so-called V-model, have been implemented [3]. These comprehensive approaches are able to support simultaneous development of mechanical, electrical, and electronics systems including software. In addition, the support starts at system specification and follows all way down to component level and up again to the final product as illustrated in Figure 1.

Mathematical modeling of components and their thermodynamic behavior is crucial in order to connect the mechanical, electrical, and electronics systems from the very beginning of the development approach. AVL has more than 50 years of experience in drive train and drive train component development including the transition from mechanical-oriented development approaches to new comprehensive approaches. This experience is used to apply the V-model approach onto SOFC and SOEC system

development where the integrated open development platform (IODP) of AVL supports to coordinate the different tasks.

Figure 1. Exemplary V-model approach from the automotive industry

2. Simulations

For system simulation, a comprehensive library of physical models was developed in recent years and are constantly further developed and improved for all relevant components of SOFC and SOEC system. Within this library several models are available for the same component but with different degree of detail as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Structure and pathway to set up new models with different degree of detail

This is of great benefit in terms of model calibration and calculation time. At an early stage of a system development e.g. the mass and material properties of a heat exchanger might not be defined or available. However, system layout and heat management need to be developed and validated. At this stage, a simpler model without mass and materials (cf. Figure 2) can be used. However, all models of the same component do have the same interfaces and thus can be exchanged by each other within the development phase. This is important to feed back new boundaries from e.g. supplier or test results back into the simulation and development.

Such system simulations are set up by just simply drag and drop the components into the simulation environment and connect them according to a flow chart. Additional tools allows to get out as much as possible from one simple simulation. This includes e.g. component specifications, empirical models of individual and system behavior, software verification and validation, optimized operations strategies, and many more. This already describes the importance of such mathematical models in order to connect the different branches within the V-model (cf. SW, HW, and mechanics in Figure 1).

3. Results

Within this chapter the above described approach and tools are presented by the example of three different cases: Case (i): Figure 3 shows the result of a stack test and the related simulation data based on a simple 0D model. The 0D model is a physical model considering cell number and active surface are as input and the area specific residence (ASR) as calibration parameter. The results show that the deviation between experimental data and simulation is within 2% and confirm that such a simplified stack model can be perfectly used for system architecture development.

Figure 3. System current and voltage of a anode supported cell stack based on a real world experiment and virtual characterization via a simple 0D model

Case (ii): A routine of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and neuronal network (NN) is used within AVL for designing system specific ejectors for passive anode recirculation. This routine includes a 2D model for designing the nozzle geometry and a 2D CFD model for the whole ejector design (incl. nozzle, mixing chamber, and diffusor). Figure 4 shows a typical contour plot of the velocity and pressure within an ejector for a defined nozzle geometry. Out of several CFD simulations with different boundary conditions and design variations NN are used to identify the correlation between change of parameters and ejector performance.

Figure 4. Typical contour plot of velocity and pressure within an ejector at full load operation point.

The output of the routine is a performance map of the ejector with any number of supporting points. Depending on the number of supporting points an empirical model (large number of supporting points) can be set up by NN. In addition, the performance map can also be used to calibrate a physical model (only few supporting points). Both can then be used within the system or sub-system simulation environment. This approach allows to even include complex components within plant and system models for control strategy and software validation and thus allows precise pre-calibration of a complex system and significant reduction on test bed operation and cost. In addition, the risk of component damage (in a thermal, mechanical or electric manner) is significantly reduced.

Case (iii): Within the development of a SOFC or SOEC system even small changes in efficiency of a component can have a significant influence on the overall efficiency, controllability, and life time of the overall system. Parameter studies are an excellent approach to evaluate and optimize system architectures and operating strategies. Figure 5 shows the outcome of such a parameter study for a 0D/1D system simulation including all relevant components. Within this study the efficiency of the air heat exchanger, the system pressure, as well as the stack temperature was varied via design of experiment (DoE).

Figure 5. Parameter study on system level based on DoE

Such results, as shown in Figure 5, are indispensable for system optimization and identification of crucial control parameters to keep the system within its boundary conditions. Without the support of such a strong simulation tool and environment, the connection via the different branches within the V-model is not possible and significantly reduces the benefits of such a modern development approach.

References

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